

Understanding new approaches to professional learning community practice and secondary school teacher motivation

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ABSTRACT

This study was determining the link between professional learning community (PLC) practice and teacher motivation in secondary schools in the Jeli District, Malaysia. The cross-sectional research method was chosen, and the research instrument were the Professional Learning Community Assessment-Revised (PLCA-R) and the Assessment of Teacher Motivation Questionnaire (ATMQ). The sample were used 171 from a population of 306 individuals. The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26.0 was used to analyze the study data. The result demonstrated that instructors in remote regions are working hard to guarantee that the professional learning community program is beneficial to them while also increasing their teaching motivation. The study's implications have demonstrated the importance of cultivating the practice of professional learning communities in schools. Thus, the school can make continuous improvements to improve student performance as well as be a catalyst to motivate teachers to work harder to improve the quality of teaching and learning.

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1. INTRODUCTION

According to the National Education Philosophy, education is a major contributor to the development of human capital, with good values in all aspects of student development, and an agreement has been signed with UNESCO with the goal of producing a generation that can compete globally, which is Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG4-Education 2030) [1]. As a result, the government has taken the initiative to change the national education system in order to attain this aim [2]. Thus, adopting the idea of professional learning community practices in schools is one of the objectives listed in the Malaysian Education Development Plan (PPPM) 2013-2025 to improve the quality of teacher instruction and student success [3], [4]. This is due to the fact that the practice of professional learning communities has been shown to impact teachers' willingness to continue seeking knowledge and skills so that teaching professionalism may be increased to a higher degree and acknowledged [5]. In accordance with this, the government's aim to become one of the top education centers in the southeast Asian area necessitates a number of adjustments in order to improve the quality of the country's education system [6].

As a result, hardworking school personnel display great levels of enthusiasm and a strong feeling of love for school by demonstrating high dedication at all times without expecting rewards in order to witness their kids' achievement [7]. In reality, administrators' practice and leadership qualities were discovered to be able to impact teacher motivation [8]–[10]. Furthermore, the practice of this professional learning community is to create excellent ties between school personnel and the outside community in order to enhance student success and school performance [3]. Thus, the collaborative culture used to improve teachers' knowledge and abilities, particularly in low socioeconomic regions, is viewed as a successful method for teacher professionalism development since it saves money on logistics and payments to external speakers [11]. Professional learning community practices were developed to assist instructors to enhance their teaching and learning by transitioning from traditional techniques to more quality and effective approaches [12]. This, in turn, can minimize the isolation of teachers who prefer to work alone, are less skilled, and are less motivated, allowing for more added value in teaching quality [9].

Furthermore, the practice of professional learning communities has been proven to improve positive values among students, such as demonstrating empathy for others through support for programs, field projects, being involved during class discussions, and completing school tasks (homework) in a specific time frame [13]. This creates the idea that teachers' and school leaders' engagement in establishing the practice of professional learning communities may not only increase student success but also instill positive values in them. When school leaders and teachers work together and are familiar with the needs of kids, all student issues may be addressed quickly by school leaders and their instructors [12].

A professional learning community is defined by Hord [14] as a collaborative practice between educators, teachers, and students, as well as schools and communities, to add value to research findings, assessments, and actions in order to continuously improve student achievement while ensuring the quality of teacher teaching remains a priority. According to Abdullah [11], a professional learning community is a method of teamwork among school personnel that involves conducting bilateral discussions with more experienced and skilled teachers, exploring and refining appropriate practices, and sharing the school's vision and mission while contributing collectively. According to DuFour and Eaker [15], a professional learning community is described as collaboration among dedicated instructors working as a team to improve the quality of teaching and learning. Furthermore, according to Zaw and Phong [4], a professional learning community is defined as ongoing engagement and support by colleagues to train and advise other teachers as well as exchange information to enhance teacher professional growth. The professional learning communities can be identified as an effective effort of educators, school administrators, learners, and communities to improve education.

Bektaş, Kılınç, and Gümüş [16] showed that professional learning communities may not only improve the quality of instructors' education but also provide teachers the freedom to make decisions and foster social connections among students. Indeed, professional learning communities may bridge the gap between leaders and teachers, minimize teacher isolation, and give encouragement and support among dedicated school personnel in order to enhance student accomplishment with excellence [7]. Furthermore, professional learning communities have been identified as a small collaborative team that needs each other, works together, enables effective learning, and provides opportunities for collectively exchanging ideas, reflecting on, and sharing knowledge for the sake of educational sustainability [17]. This is necessary so that the professional learning community practice can be used as a model of organizational management in strengthening teaching in order to achieve the concept of continuous learning, producing quality teacher teaching through collaboration, integration, and leadership sharing among school people [18].

Thus, establishing a professional learning community is a strong and real way for producing students in the classroom via the use of effective, methodical, and proactive teaching [12]. This is supported by a study conducted by Derk [19], which discovered that teachers who are given support, encouragement, and attention will be a catalyst for student achievement; in fact, these teachers will use all available resources, including modern and up-to-date teaching aids, with the main goal of ensuring that students continue to excel. Essentially, research has demonstrated that the practice of professional learning communities is the dedicated collaboration demonstrated by school administrators and teachers during the information sharing process [20]. Finally, school leaders and teachers who form a network of collaboration and dedication will provide intelligent ideas for resolving challenges and will always exchange best practices for producing successful teaching in order to ensure the national education system's long-term viability [21].

Motivation is derived from the Latin word 'movere', which means to push or move. According to Asykar and Riyanto [22], the features of motivation consist of five factors: intrinsic process, instrumental, outward self-concept, internal self-concept, and established objectives. Motivation may also be described as a person's aspirations that affect their actions and dedication [23], [24]. Backs up this description by defining motivation as "intrinsic and extrinsic elements that will retain responsibility for the work assigned in attaining personal objectives." In the face of an ever-changing learning environment, teacher motivation must be maintained and adapted to the changing environment by providing highly qualified and competent

teachers, so that student performance is not jeopardized [25]. Furthermore, teacher motivation is frequently linked to physiological processes that influence teacher behavior in order to attain school goals [26].

According to Patrick [27], teacher motivation is strongly connected to student excellence, education system improvement, and impact the psychology of teachers, all of which require attention and further study as empirical proof. While Pourrahimi and Dizgah [28] define motivation as a sincere desire that determines an individual's inner strength; thereby improving performance, skills, shaping behavior, influencing cognitive factors that is the learning process that determines the achievement of an organization's goals in an environment is effective [29]. According to Jabeen, Khan, and Manzoor [30], motivation is the ability to inspire an individual to go ahead or even accomplish something, acting as a catalyst for a person to carry out his work attentively in order to achieve organizational goals. As a result, it can be stated that a high degree of teacher motivation may foster a responsible attitude, constantly be proactive, and discover alternative methods to address issues, where these traits have a significant impact on student success [31].

The government established Professional Learning Community (PLC) in 2011 to improve the quality of teacher teaching and school leadership [18], [20] based on practices used in developed countries to improve student performance [21]. Nonetheless, western researchers have found professional learning community practices difficult to implement [32]–[34], because school personnel continue to lack information and in-depth knowledge about this practice, resulting in the cultivation of professional learning communities [8]. Furthermore, school administrators who are not open-minded, incompetent, or innovative, and who do not offer teachers authority to make decisions and handle problems exacerbate the challenge of creating and establishing professional learning community practices in schools [35].

School leaders were discovered to be autocratic and less skilled in strategic management of schools by placing an excessive workload on the shoulders of teachers, causing teachers to be stressed and just be followers and carry out tasks simply without being able to unearth such teachers' creativity [8]. Furthermore, principal's leadership may impact professional learning community practices and government initiatives by putting competent principals in place, which has been demonstrated to increase students' success when professional learning communities are used [36]. Indeed, Shuib and Yunus [20] said that the use of professional learning communities to promote learning and teacher teaching quality is still not entirely possible in the nation. Professional learning community activities, on the other hand, are frequently the major objective for increasing student success and the quality of teachers' teaching so that educational transformation may occur [37]. This assertion is confirmed by Hassan and Ismail [9], who discovered that professional learning community activities should result in change in teacher pedagogy when school leaders and peers provide systematic support and direction.

Teacher motivation is frequently associated with behaviors, performance, and goals that direct a teacher to act and demonstrate an attitude toward the task entrusted to them, because teachers serve as the foundation for increasing students' motivation through effective teaching quality and bond formation relationship between the instructor and the learner [38]. As a result, maintaining and improving teacher motivation is critical since it has an influence on the classroom, as well as the school structure and community. Thus, the Ministry of Education has taken the initiative by establishing a professional learning community aimed at creating a favorable atmosphere to enhance motivation and encourage instructors to collaborate in order to improve students' performance [20]. However, if leaders and colleagues do not perform their respective responsibilities throughout the mentoring process, teachers will choose to carry out conventional teaching activities [17], working alone and in isolation, over other colleagues [7]. Furthermore, teachers will become less competent, efficient, and motivated while carrying out their tasks [39].

In reality, teachers' motivation will be harmed, as will their efficiency and abilities in obtaining material to improve the quality of teaching and solely using textbooks as the primary reference to satisfy students' examination demands [9], [21]. Teachers are overburdened with non-academic responsibilities such as student affairs management, school administration, and co-curricular management, all of which contribute to a loss in teacher motivation and, as a result, teacher job efficiency [40]. Furthermore, according to a 2011 assessment by the Academy of Higher Education Leadership (AKEPT), just 50% of lectures were presented well, with the remainder being less encouraging. This is supported by the PPPM 2013-2025 research, which found that over half of the 41 schools studied do not employ high-level learning styles and even prefer to use conventional techniques in the process of knowledge acquisition [21]. This circumstance suggests that teachers are less motivated to alter their teaching and learning techniques in order to increase student accomplishment as well as the performance of the school organization they represent. In this regard, figures suggest that 60% of teachers will continue to teach for another 20 years, which is a significant issue that the government must address in order to properly adopt professional learning community methods [21].

As a result, the Ministry of Education has taken severe measures, such as establishing a professional learning community in schools, so that low-motivated teachers may be mentored from time to time by those in authority. Therefore, it will increasing teachers' passion, determination, high effort, and motivation. In fact,

Senin [41] stated that the objectives of the implementation of professional learning communities are unclear. It has resulted in a decline in teacher motivation and creativity when the leadership, colleagues, and work environment do not support the tasks to be completed by teachers, even when follow-up action is taken, following the completion of monitoring.

According to the study of the Malaysian Board of Inspectors and Quality Assurance, 85% of the teaching quality in the country is concerning, with only 15% at a good or exceptional level [21]. This means that there are weaknesses in teachers' teaching in schools that need to be strengthened further through the practice of professional learning communities in order to stimulate and enhance teacher motivation, because the culture of collaboration used in the practice of professional learning communities is the main driver of teachers' efforts to achieve school goals [17], [42]. In this regard, this method of stimulating teacher motivation is important to encourage teachers to provide feedback and have a reflective dialogue for the continuous proliferation of ideas so that their self-motivation and creativity in teaching and learning can be more easily highlighted, which not only increase the level of teacher professionalism but also teachers' teaching motivation. This is supported by previous studies [43], [44], which discovered that most teachers who are less motivated prefer to isolate, work alone, share less experience, do not open communication space, are difficult to interact, and are not interested in bilateral discussions, and this will not only affect the teachers' performance but also their level of professional development.

As a result, the purpose of this research is to investigate the link between the independent factors of professional learning community practice and the dependent variables of teacher motivation in day secondary schools in Jeli District, Kelantan, Malaysia. The study also looks at the elements of professional learning communities' activities, such as value and vision sharing, collective learning, sharing private practices, and situation support. Thus, the hypothesis of the study: i) There is no substantial link between leadership partnership and leadership support and teacher motivation in Jeli District secondary schools (Ho1); ii) There is no substantial link between value and vision sharing and teacher motivation in Jeli District secondary schools (Ho2); iii) There is no substantial link between collective learning and application and teacher motivation in Jeli District secondary schools (Ho3); iv) There is no substantial link between private practice sharing and teacher motivation in Jeli District secondary schools (Ho4); v) There is no substantial link between situation support and teacher motivation in Jeli District secondary schools (Ho5).

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Demographics and sampling

The sample size for this study was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's population proportion table [45]. The study included 171 participants, 60 male teachers and 111 female instructors from five secondary schools in the Jeli District of Kelantan, Malaysia. The justification for selecting the Jeli District of Kelantan is due to poor performance results. The actual population of the study includes a total of 306 teachers who are currently teaching in the five schools, according to data acquired from the Jeli District Education Office. There were 108 male instructors and 198 female teachers from diverse backgrounds and degrees of schooling among the 306 teachers. Thus, based on Krejcie and Morgan's [45] population percentage table, a total of 187 questionnaires, including 10% over sampling, were delivered to study respondents via school principals. The questionnaire response rate is 91.44 %. A return rate of more than 40% is considered satisfactory. In general, this study used a basic random sample approach, thus the research questionnaire was sent to all instructors in five secondary schools in the Jeli District of Kelantan, as well as the school administration. A simple random sampling method may be employed if the ratio of male to female instructors is not balanced, allowing the sampling error to be decreased and the sample size to approach the population's real size.

2.2. Instruments for research

2.2.1. Professional learning community

The professional learning community assessment-revised (PLCA-R) questionnaire, adapted from Olivier and Hipp [46], was used to assess the independent variables of professional learning community practice. It consists of 52 items organized into five dimensions: partnership and leadership support; value and vision sharing; collective learning and application; private practice sharing; and situational support. Respondents will complete the questionnaire by marking 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neutral, 4=agree, and 5=strongly agree on a 5-point Likert scale. Respondents using this approach just need to mark the Likert scale based on the appropriateness and agreement to the questions on the instrument. In this study, the Cronbach's alpha reliability score for the independent variable of the professional learning community was ($\alpha=0.972$). Internal consistency with Cronbach alpha above .70 is considered trustworthy and satisfactory [47]. As a result, professional learning communities' tools are appropriate for use in this study.

2.2.2. Motivation of teachers

The assessment of teacher motivation questionnaire (ATMQ) instrument developed by Gokce [31] is used to measure the dependent variables of teacher motivation in this study, which consists of 29 items divided into two dimensions, namely the dimension of needs met and the dimension of importance level of needs based on Maslow's hierarchy of needs. A five-point Likert scale was utilized in the study questionnaire: 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neutral, 4=agree, and 5=strongly agree. Respondents just need to indicate the approval scale for the items presented in this instrument, when utilizing this five-point Likert scale. In this study, the Cronbach's alpha reliability score for the dependent variable of teacher motivation was ($\alpha=0.947$). As a result, this research instrument's questionnaire is consistent, accurate, exact, consistent, and trustworthy [47].

2.2.3. Research methodologies

Several steps must be undertaken prior to conducting a study. The first stage is for researchers to request authorization from the Awang Had Salleh Graduate School (AHSGS) at Universiti Utara Malaysia. After gaining authorization from AHSGS, researchers must request for clearance from the Ministry of Education's Research and Policy Planning Division (EPRD) online at <https://eras.moe.gov.my>. The EPRD served as the Ministry of Education's ethical committee for data gathered from schools. Following authorization and approval from the EPRD, researchers must request in writing for permission from the Kelantan State Education Department (JPN) and the Jeli District Education Office (PPD). Once the JPN and PPD have granted authorization to conduct the study, the researcher must notify the principal of the study school, as well as provide a description of the research techniques to be used.

The study instrument was delivered to the school, together with the approval letter from EPRD and JPN, to be distributed and responded by the teachers. Based on the study population, as many as 306 questionnaires were delivered in this study. In addition, instructors will have seven days to complete the questionnaire. If the seven-day timeframe is insufficient, the researcher will extend it for another seven days to provide instructors time to respond to the questionnaire that has been issued. The researchers will next gather a questionnaire, and the results will be put into SPSS version 26 for data analysis. Finally, the researchers will produce a report based on the outcomes of the data analysis

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Respondent demographic

The sole objective of this part is to present the study findings which are divided based on the objectives highlighted. The first of this study as present the respondent demography using descriptive statistics, second id the result of examine data analysis. The data present gender that 35.1% of the subjects for male (60 teachers) while the other 64.9% were found to be females (111 teachers). Further demographic details were related to respondent's age and teaching experiences presented in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively.

Table 1. Distribution of age among respondent

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Less than 25 years old	0	0
26-30 years old	4	2.3
31-35 years old	13	7.6
36-40 years old	45	26.3
41-45 years old	44	25.7
46-50 years old	31	18.1
More than 50 years old	34	19.9
Total	171	100.0

Table 2. Distribution of teaching experience

Teaching experience	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Less than 10 years	19	11.1
10-20 years	87	50.9
21-30 years	60	35.1
More than 30 years	5	2.9
Total	171	100.0

3.2. Leadership partnerships and support

The results of the analysis in Table 3 showed that the dimensions of partnership and leadership support had a strong and significant positive relationship with teacher motivation where the value of the correlation coefficient ($r=0.612$, $p=0.001$, $p<0.05$). This demonstrates that collaboration and leadership support have successfully enhanced teacher motivation. The more school leaders exercise collaboration and leadership support, the more motivated teachers are to carry out their role as educators in the school. This study's findings refute the null hypothesis, which claims that there is no meaningful association between these two factors.

Table 3. The relationship between partnership and leadership support with teacher motivation

Teacher motivation		Partnership and leadership support	
Teacher motivation	Correlation	1	.612**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	171	171

** $p<0.01$

3.3. Sharing values and vision

Table 4 displays the results of Pearson correlation ($r=0.760$, $p=0.001$, $p<0.05$) between the dimensions of value and vision sharing with teacher motivation in Jeli District secondary schools. The table confirmed the relationship and the importance of teacher motivation affecting the instructor's performance. The dimension of value and vision sharing among school leaders successfully boosts teacher motivation. School leaders who share beliefs and vision with teachers will have a beneficial impact on teacher motivation in the schools involved.

Table 4. Relationship between values and vision sharing with teacher motivation

Teacher motivation		Values and vision sharing	
Teacher motivation	Correlation	1	.760**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	171	171

** $p<0.01$

3.4. Collective learning and applications

Based on the results of Pearson correlation analysis shown in Table 5, it was found that the dimensions of collective learning and application have a strong and significant positive relationship with teacher motivation in Jeli District secondary schools that is the value of correlation coefficient ($r=0.799$, $p=0.001$, $p<0.05$). The result show strong relationship between collective learning and application in their job will be more motivated. Teachers are likewise highly motivated to improve their teaching skills through collaborative learning and application. The null hypothesis, which claims that there is no significant link between these two variables, is refuted by this finding.

Table 5. Relationship between collective learning and application with teacher motivation

Teacher motivation		Collective learning and application	
Teacher motivation	Correlation	1	.799**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	171	171

** $p<0.01$

3.5. Private practice sharing

Table 6 shows the results of the private practice sharing dimension has a strong and significant positive relationship with teacher motivation where the value of the correlation coefficient ($r=0.713$, $p=0.001$, $p>0.05$). The table show strongly confirmed the teacher motivation was affected to teaching and practice sharing among school members. Teachers who participate in professional learning communities that practice sharing are highly motivated to carry out their responsibilities at school. They share teaching techniques and resources, as well as organize group discussions. This data contradicts the null hypothesis, which asserts that there is no significant association between practice sharing and increased motivation among instructors active in professional learning communities.

Table 6. Relationship between private practice sharing with teacher motivation

Teacher motivation		Private practice sharing	
Teacher motivation	Correlation	1	.713**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	171	171

**p<.01

3.6. Situational support

The results of Pearson correlation coefficient in Table 7 for the dimension of situation support with teacher motivation in Jeli District secondary school has a strong and significant positive relationship with teacher motivation in the school that is the value of correlation coefficient ($r=0.787$, $p=0.001$, $p<0.05$). The results promoted teacher motivation have to support situation to enhance teacher performance. School leaders who provide situational assistance will have a beneficial impact on teachers' motivation to carry out their obligations as teachers in the school. As a result, teachers have high levels of motivation and excellent work performance. This study's findings contradict the null hypothesis, which asserts that situational support has no meaningful association with the motivation of the teachers participated in the study.

Table 7. Relationship between situational support and teacher motivation

Teacher motivation		Situational support	
Teacher motivation	Correlation	1	.787**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	171	171

**p<.001

3.7. Discussion

Data analysis using Pearson correlation to identify the relationship between professional learning community practices and teacher motivation in Jeli District secondary schools revealed that the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between professional learning community practices and teacher motivation in the school was rejected. This is because the professional learning community's practice and its five dimensions were discovered to have a strong and substantial positive significance relationship with the dependent variables of teacher motivation in the school. This is most likely due to the fact that the majority of respondents had teaching experience ranging from 10 to 20 years (50.9%), 21 to 30 years (35.1%), fewer than 10 years (11.1%), and more than 30 years (2.9%). The conclusions of this study are confirmed by Esdras and Andala [48], who discovered that without intrinsic and extrinsic variables, teacher motivation will suffer, affecting the instructor's performance. As a result, with motivated teachers, professional learning community practices may be implemented more quickly because teachers will continue to offer a high commitment so that these practices can be nurtured in schools [2].

Moreover, this study found that all four professional learning community aspects had a positive association with teacher motivations. This demonstrates that professional learning professional programmed provide beneficial benefits among programmed teachers. Teachers in this community develop an interest in collaborating with other teachers to improve teaching and learning materials, are supportive of one another, ready to share, and may have had solid support from Jeli's schools and education district office. This statement is supported by Zhang, Yin, and Wang [49], who discovered that the factor of increasing teacher motivation is influenced by teachers' collective effectiveness and job satisfaction, with highly motivated teachers carrying out responsibilities effectively during the teaching and learning process. This has resulted in the successful deployment of professional learning community methods.

Furthermore, the study done by Othman *et al.* [50] confirmed the conclusions of this study, with the results revealing a positive and substantial link between the dimensions of collective learning and situational support. According to them, teachers' positive motivation has encouraged their job dedication, and teachers will work harder to build a school community that embraces a collaborative culture throughout the implementation of professional learning communities. In fact, previous research findings [51] concur that teacher motivation has a strong link with teacher teaching performance and is an essential factor affecting the implementation of professional learning community activities in schools. On the other hand, teacher motivation had minimal influence on collaboration among school personnel and teachers' collective learning to establish a strong professional learning community team to enhance student achievement [43]. This statement is supported by Zaw and Phong [4], who discovered that, despite the implementation of professional learning community practices, teacher motivation is less encouraging during the process of

knowledge sharing among school organization members, school vision and mission sharing, and teaching reflection. However, neither of the aforementioned scenarios [4], [43] applies to the respondents in this study.

This study, on the other hand, discovered that teacher motivation had a large and extremely strong association with teacher commitment. The outcomes of this study were similar with [23], who showed that intrinsic variables affected teacher motivation, which also influenced normative and emotional commitment of teachers during the educational process. Perhaps the school administrators of the chosen school provided teachers with full support for the programs since teachers would be disheartened without it. According to Rhoda [24], if the school disregards teacher welfare and fails to provide appropriate teaching aids, teacher motivation declines, making it more difficult for the school to create professional learning community practices in schools.

On the other side, it is thought that these teachers are highly motivated to lead the professional learning community. This is true because poor teacher motivation lowers teachers' reactions to school rules and regulations, and it also has an influence on a sense of duty, trust, and all opportunities. Uninspired teachers look down on it because they wish to distinguish themselves in all aspects of educational needs provided by the school [25]. This statement is supported further by Mansor, Nasaruddin, and Hamid [52], who found that when teacher motivation is high, the relationship between school people and leaders, between teachers and colleagues, between teachers and students, or between teachers and the community outside of school improves. Indeed, improved teacher motivation, according to Fei and Han [38], will impact how leaders, teachers, and students assess schools based on their respective perspectives. To support this claim, Feriyanti and Usman [18] discovered that teachers who were provided stimuli to promote self-motivation showed a favorable shift in which the degree of discipline among teachers improved when school leaders always encouraged and motivated teachers -the instructor. In fact, the study by Tiop and Talip [53] does not deny this statement, stating that high teacher motivation is always a catalyst to effective leadership demonstrated by principals, particularly for principals who intend to integrate technology and ICT in schools because the presence of teachers who are always motivated and enthusiastic affects the principal's motivation. As a result, improved teacher motivation will ensure the successful adoption of professional learning community activities in schools.

Nonetheless, Antin and Dzulkifli [40] observed in a review of the literature that teacher motivation has decreased as a result of increasing workload and non-pedagogically relevant duties that must be done. This circumstance has, to some extent, dampened teachers' passion for giving the best education possible. This was not the case in this study, as teachers who participated in the professional learning community did not perceive the program as a burden since they saw it as part of their in-service training to improve their teaching abilities. Perhaps the more excited people are about the program; the more motivated they are to improve their teaching. This claim is confirmed by a study conducted by Karuppanan, Duari, and Manogharan [54], who revealed that high teacher motivation also plays a part in determining the success or failure of professional learning community practices implementation in the school. Indeed, Mayan and Mansor [17] discovered that teacher motivation can influence the practice of professional learning communities in which teachers who show seriousness and enthusiasm will always do their best to succeed in all school planning, always collaborate with colleagues, and are not afraid to share knowledge in addition to motivating and being a role model to members of the organization. As a result, professional learning communities must be vigorously practiced and promoted in schools. This is because participation in professional learning communities may help teachers grow and enhance their quality during the ongoing teaching and learning process [12].

On the other hand, Yaakob *et al.* [55] further demonstrate that management is an important operation that works as a team and has a collective goal. Without the support of the principal, the program will be unable to fulfil its objectives and retain the benefits of commitment, lowering student learning and teaching motivation both in schools and in classrooms. However, Khun-Inkeeree *et al.* [56] advised that the headteacher obtain the professional competence necessary to plan, assess, mentor, and evaluate educational achievement. The State Education Department should train more headteachers in professional learning community supervision skills to ensure teachers' continued success in teaching competency and motivation. On the other side, the program's supervision abilities should not be overlooked, and headteachers should study and be taught to equip themselves. The goal of a professional learning community cannot be realized without professional practical teaching, corporate communication competence, and supervisory experience on the part of the instructor and headteacher. In this regard, it is important to guarantee that the supervisory process is carried out in accordance with the established rules and specifications. As a result, effective supervision will explicitly improve classroom performance [57]. Furthermore, Kasa *et al.* [58] stated that the assessment of teaching and learning should not be overlooked because the findings of their study indicate that these supervisions have to do with the teacher's self-efficacy, which will improve their motivation to teach, and should not be ignored as a component in the school's success.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the findings of this study indicated that teachers and leaders in the rural area are working together to ensure that the professional learning community program is achieving its goals of keeping teachers' teaching and materials up to date, and that teacher-teacher collaboration is at an excellent level. It appears that the program is also encouraged and supported by the principal's instructors who regard teaching and instruction as a process that will not impede their professional development as teachers should be held responsible by operational supervisors. The supervisors frequently create strong relationships in order to construct a tangible social network are extremely important in realizing the school's strategic planning through the introduction of professional learning communities, so that the degree of teacher motivation is frequently increased. Schools can be more effective if instructors and administrators can meet the stated goals and expectations for students' abilities, behaviors, achievements, and teamwork. As a consequence, the professional learning community should be included in programs of teaching and learning hybrid material product, supervisory skills program, higher order thinking skills ability, and a pleasant cooperative learning environment among instructors by infusing components of 3D visual interactions that are readily acquired.

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